

OCCASIONAL SYNONYMS EXPRESSING HONESTY AND THEIR SEMANTIC STRUCTURE AND MEANINGS

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Abstract. *In this article, there is an explanation of the occurrences of occasionalism and neologism in our language and the reasons for their appearance. Differences and similarities between these two existing terms and phenomena are analyzed. Occasional synonyms of honesty in our language and their semantic structure and meanings are explained with the help of various examples.*

Keywords: *occasional, neologism, semantic, occasionalism, occasional synonyms.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada tilimizda mavjud bo‘lgan okkozional birliklar va neologizm hodisalarining izohi va payda bo‘lish sabablari izohlangan. Bu ikkala terminning va til hodisalarining ozaro farqi hamda qiyosiy jihatlari tahlil etilgan. Tilimizdagi “halollik” konseptiga oid okkozional sinonimlar va ularning semantik strukturasi hamda ma’nolari turli xil misollar yordamida yoritib berilgan.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *okkozional, neologizm, semantik, okkozionalizm, okkozional sinonimlar.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье дается объяснение возникновения окказионализма и неологизма в нашем языке и причины их появления. Анализируются различия и сходства этих двух существующих терминов и явлений. Окказиональные синонимы честности в нашем языке, их смысловая структура и значения поясняются с помощью различных примеров.*

Ключевые слова: *окказионализм, неологизм, семантика, окказионализм, окказиональные синонимы.*

Introduction

The emergence of new words in our language occurs through various methods, and such words can be created by diverse means. Naturally, this process is marked by the formation of derived terms as part of linguistic activity, as well as the introduction of new terms resulting from social interactions.

Approximately 400 new words enter our language each year¹. However, not all of these words are interpreted as new lexical units or widely adopted by speakers. Newly emerged units are created through productive word formation methods and structures. The phenomenon of occasionalism refers to the creation or invention of new, uncommon lexical units within speech, typically arising from the linguistic needs of certain individuals—such as artists, scientists, or writers—who wish to convey their thoughts in a clear, simple, precise, and concise manner or to portray an image vividly. Occasional words are crafted and employed by a specific individual to capture objects, people, or events in a detailed, multi-faceted way, reflecting their personal perspective and purpose. These occasional lexical units are generated when the language’s existing options and vocabulary are insufficient for the creator to express the chosen object in a satisfactory and precise manner.

¹ N.R.Umarova, X.I.Umarova, F.A.Yakubova “Okkozional birliklarning vujudga kelishi” – “Yevrosiyo ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali”, 2020, 105-bet.

The term “occasionalism” is derived from the Latin word “occasionalis”, meaning “accidental” or “incidental”. One of the linguistic dictionaries defines this term as follows: "A unique lexical unit that does not conform to generally accepted usages and is embedded within a specific text"². Occasionalisms are widely used not only within the scope of affixes that form words and structures but also in creating entirely new, unique lexical meanings through the use of morphemes. Sometimes, the terms “occasionalism” and “neologism”, as well as the linguistic phenomena they represent, are inaccurately used or insufficiently distinguished. Indeed, these two concepts and phenomena differ from each other in certain respects, both in terms of meaning and structure.

These two phenomena share certain similar characteristics: both carry a sense of novelty, and each is created by a particular author. However, they also differ in key ways. A “neologism” is a linguistic unit that exists within the lexicon and, over time, loses its novelty to become a conventional term. “Occasionalism”, on the other hand, is a speech unit that does not exist within the lexicon and is used within a specific speech context.

Occasionalism is a phenomenon of speech in which the author employs occasional units to express personal thoughts and reflections. For example, various occasional units may be used within speech to convey the concept of "honesty." Occasional words are unique, unconventional creations that do not exist in the common or literary lexicon; rather, they are formed and used by an individual within a specific context, arising from the needs of the particular situation or content³. For instance, in colloquial language, the lexeme “honesty” can sometimes be expressed through the phrase "toza odam" (literally, "clean person"). This occasional expression is not formed through derivational or inflectional affixes; rather, it combines two independent words with distinct meanings to create a new, derived expression conveying an original meaning. In his novel “Navoi”, writer Oybek uses the phrase "Alisher yuragi toza odam edi" ("Alisher was a pure-hearted person") in reference to Alisher Navoi. Within this metaphorical expression, "toza odam" is used to convey meanings like “honest,” “generous,” and “one who does not betray others’ rights.” By employing this phrase, Oybek emphasizes Navoi’s deep integrity and his readiness to assist those in need around him. Through this choice of words, the author intensifies the meaning of honesty and succeeds in conveying his expressive intent more profoundly. In his novel “O’tkan Kunlar” (“Days Gone By”), Abdulla Kodiriy uses the expression “toza odam” (pure-hearted person) in the line: “An honest and pure-hearted person must first be honest with themselves.” Here, Kodiriy employs “toza odam” to emphasize personal integrity, suggesting that genuine honesty begins with one’s own self.

In the “Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language”(O‘zbek tili izohli lug‘ati), the phrase “to‘g‘ri bo‘lmoq” (to be upright) is sometimes used with the meanings "to be fair, conscientious, and honest"⁴. An example is given from an Uzbek proverb: “If you are upright, you will grow and blossom; if you are crooked, you will grow and turn to ashes.” Here, “to‘g‘ri bo‘lmoq” emphasizes the importance of approaching every task conscientiously and with integrity, highlighting honesty and fairness as qualities that contribute to a person’s development into a complete individual. In the following sentence, “to‘g‘ri bo‘lmoq” is also used as an

² Розинтель Д.Э., Теленкова М.А. Словарь – справочник лингвистических терминов. М.:Просвещение. 1967.С.197

³ Toshaliyeva S. O‘zbek tilida okkazional so‘z yasalishi: Filol. Fanlari nomzodi ... dis. –T.,1998

⁴ O‘zbek tilining izohli lug‘ati: 80000 dan ortiq so‘z va so‘z birikmasi. J. I. – Toshkent: O‘zME, 2022.

equivalent to the concept of "honesty": "If you had been upright, would these accusations have come to me!" — N. Safarov, "Hayot maktabi"(The school of life).

One occasional synonym for the lexeme "honest" is the phrase "xasga ham xiyonat qilmaydigan" (one who wouldn't betray even a twig). This phrase conveys the sense of an "honest person" who would never betray anyone's trust or rights. It is a coined expression, created by combining two independent words through specific methods. If we examine the semantics of each word in this phrase, we see that "twig" refers to a small, dry branch or stick and is a noun, while the verb "to betray" combines with it to form an expression meaning a "person with integrity." In Muxtor Ashurov's work "Yulduzlar" (Stars), the sentence "I am a person who wouldn't betray even a twig" uses this phrase to convey the sense of an "upright person," "person of integrity," or "honest" individual.

The phrase "person of integrity" also appears widely in Uzbek literature with the meaning of "honest." In Abdulla Kodiriy's "O'tkan Kunlar" (Days Gone By), for instance, the phrase "person of integrity" is used to convey someone's moral character and honesty in fulfilling their duties. In the novel, the phrase "He was, indeed, a person of integrity" highlights the moral uprightness and honesty of the character Husniddin.

As noted, the process of creating new words and lexical units in our language occurs through various methods. The term "occasionalism" refers to new words or expressions coined by a particular individual. These words do not exist in traditional dictionaries but are crafted uniquely based on specific circumstances and needs. Such occasional expressions exist not only in an individual's speech but also reflect the unique aspects of language and culture. Through the concept of honesty and its synonyms, writers vividly portray social values, human virtues, and ethical norms in their works. Thus, occasionalisms and their contexts play an essential role in the development of language and literature, enabling the expression of new ideas, emotions, and experiences. The ideas presented in this article offer deeper insight into the semantic structure of the term "honesty" and its occasional synonyms. This, in turn, expands the richness of Uzbek literature and its representation in literary works.

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